

D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

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Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

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Executive Summary

BioRural seeks to establish a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. BioRural will contribute to bridge the gap between the novel high-end bio-based solutions currently available and the everyday rural life in Europe by:

- evaluating and assessing the current state of the European rural bioeconomy,
- identifying grassroots needs and ideas,
- fostering effective knowledge and information exchange,
- looking into potential opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

This way, BioRural will develop a transition framework towards a sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, and just circular Bioeconomy across all Europe at local and regional scale and support innovators to scale-up inclusive and small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. To do so, the project will:

- (i) Assess and evaluate the **current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy** in the EU and identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (ii) Create four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that will form a **European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)**;
- (iii) Assess and promote **success stories** of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (iv) Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool, named **BioRural Toolkit**;
- (v) Facilitate knowledge exchange and **capacity building** for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops in local, regional, and European level;
- (vi) Create **rural development blueprints** for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- (vii) Disseminate and communicate all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the intended stakeholders.

The aim of this document is to present a clear and coherent dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy which will serve as a cornerstone for all the outreach activities envisaged to be carried out throughout the project. Particular attention is given to the BioRural's multi-actor approach, considering all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from the diverse set of partners and stakeholders ensuring broad communication throughout the project's course.

This document is the first iteration of the DEC plan which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation (M18) and will be conclude to the documentation of the attained results of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (M36).

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AKIS	Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems
DEC	Dissemination Exploitation and Communication
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
ERBN	European Rural Bioeconomy Network
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RBPs	Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SOSTAC	Situation, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Action, Control

1 Introduction

1.1 Project overview

Challenge

The EU economy is heavily reliant on linear production systems and non-renewable resources and materials. Since the extraction of fossil fuels continues to release more carbon into the atmosphere, it exacerbates already major environmental and climatic issues and the well-known greenhouse effect. Further, climate change has an impact on the entire economy in addition to having an immediate consequence on the environment and humans.

The climate change impact over food security, human health, migratory flows, biodiversity loss and rising sea levels, will lead to a decline in productivity and wealth creation.

In this context, the bioeconomy has a key role to play.

Strengthening Europe’s bioeconomy can significantly accelerate progress towards achieving key EU policy objectives, such as transitioning to a circular economy, becoming climate neutral by 2050, and strengthening the EU industrial base.

BioRural aims to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network under which related stakeholders cooperate to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. This framework will contribute to bridging the gap between the available novel high-end bio-based solutions and the everyday European rural life by assessing the existing situation of European rural Bioeconomy, capturing grassroots-level needs and ideas, promoting effective exchange of knowledge and information, and investigating the possible opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

BioRural is built on a three-pillar intervention scheme:

Table 1: BioRural three-pillar intervention scheme

Pillar 1 - Knowledge	Pillar 2 - Network	Pillar 3 – Business Models
<p>1 overview of the EU Bioeconomy current status</p> <p>440 interviews with end users/experts</p> <p>5 knowledge exchange workshops</p>	<p>1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)</p> <p>4 Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms - RBPs</p> <p>8 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories</p> <p>42 capacity building workshops</p> <p>4 Regional workshops</p> <p>1 European Bioeconomy Challenge</p>	<p>5 Business model blueprints (for each of the main Bioeconomy themes)</p> <p>1 Post project sustainability plan</p>

BioRural's key activities

BioRural's workplan is comprised of the following key activities:

- Assessment and evaluation of the current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy in the EU and identification of the factors affecting innovation, adoption, and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Creation of four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that form a European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN);
- Assessment and promotion of success stories of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Development and continuous optimization of an online open stakeholders' tool, named BioRural Toolkit;
- Facilitation of knowledge exchange and capacity building for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops in local, regional, and European level;
- Creation of rural development blueprints for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- Dissemination and communication of all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

Figure 1: BioRural's conceptual approach

1.2 Document scope and structure

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the targeted stakeholders. This document is the first iteration of the DEC plan which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation (M18) and will conclude to the documentation of the attained results of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (M36).

This document is comprised of the following chapters & Annexes:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project and the document's scope, structure, and objectives.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project's DEC methodology and approach, the identified target groups, and relevant key messages.

Chapter 3 delves into the specific dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels including the visual identity, communication material and the channel mix.

Chapter 4 specifies the reporting and monitoring procedures and tools, focusing on KPIs and the specific activities that will be carried out.

Chapter 5 presents the identified Key Exploitable Results, the potential pathways to bring BioRural results to all targeted user communities as well as the identified IPRs and IPR strategy followed by the project partners.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

Annex A provides the project logo variations.

Annex B presents BioRural's covers that are used on social media.

Annex C provides images of the dissemination and communication material that has already been designed including the brochure, the banner, and the press release template.

Annex D provides the deliverable template.

Annex E provides the event planning template to be used for gathering information from partners regarding the events they are already planning on attending.

Annex F provides the synergy mapping template that partners will complete with information on existing projects, networks, alliances etc., that they are currently part of and could be relevant to BioRural.

Annex G provides the publication planning template that partners will complete with information on peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other planned publications.

Annex H provides the project's brand book.

Annex I provides the template for the Identification of new KERs & IPR process

2 DEC methodology and approach

2.1 DEC objectives & time plan

The DEC plan objectives are S.M.A.R.T (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time bound) and provide a verifiable trajectory towards clear milestones and an estimated timeline to attain the goals and ensure impact maximization.

Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities are expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact. More specifically the dissemination activities will be carefully planned to ensure that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders are engaged early and actively participate during each of the project's phases. BioRural applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all the relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the below dissemination objectives:

- Bring together a critical mass of stakeholders and maximize outreach opportunities for BioRural with targeted messaging and customized content;
- Diffuse scientific and technological knowledge generated in the project and put it to productive use via capacity building under BioRural activities;
- Nurture collaborative relationships with projects, initiatives, pan-European networks of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and AKIS actors to avoid duplication of efforts, and capitalize on the results;
- Receive and utilize feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to make sure project developments are going in the right direction;
- Align and integrate dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of our reusable assets;
- Encourage new initiatives and support those already being carried out.

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, BioRural's exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring BioRural results to all targeted stakeholders (including bio-based raw material producers, bio-based industries, rural and urban citizens, local and regional government, local rural schools and universities, NGOs, environmental and citizens' groups and unions). A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project's lifetime. The objectives of the project's exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results.
- Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project's results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

BioRural aims to capture the added value of project results, which will be valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project's results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialization when possible

Communication Objectives

All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project’s results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered as communication activities. In essence, communication activities are focused on maximising the visibility of the project, through widely attracting a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project’s results and benefit from the project’s advancements. To achieve this, attention will be paid to adapt the communication means, the measures, and the content both to the need and knowledge levels of the target groups as well as to the status, progress and needs of the BioRural project. To ensure that the communication measures will effectively address the project’s expectations, communication objectives have been set:

- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage positive reception and acceptance by farmers, their advisors, policy makers;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels.

Time plan

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 2) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the achievement of the objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Vision, Phase 2: Raise cognition, Phase 3: Multiplier effect, Phase 4: Sustainability) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 2: BioRural’s DEC phases

2.2 DEC methodology

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners to boost the growth of the BioRural ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximize impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level.

The BioRural DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC** model which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control.

Figure 3: BioRural DEC methodology

Situation analysis: A state-of-play analysis in which the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.

Objectives: The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication.

Tactics: Identification of the tactics that will allow BioRural consortium to implement its strategy.

Actions: The DEC plan will build upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the proposal and include the contributions expected from partners, and their distribution over the duration of the project. A living list of planned events will also be included. Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation.

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the proposal will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used together with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in Chapter 4.

2.3 Multi-actor approach

BioRural will use a multi-actor approach, considering all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to achieve the project aims and ensure broad communication from the start. Figure 4 presents the six different stakeholders' groups that are involved in BioRural.

Figure 4: BioRural’s stakeholder’s groups

Interactive innovation process

The ‘multi-actor’ approach is key for interactive innovation. The way diverse actors work well together (the ‘multi-actor approach’) is crucial for interactive innovation to deliver unique project results and benefits.

Multi-actor innovation brings together a diverse range of public and private innovation actors as shown in figure 4, with complementary types and sources of knowledge to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs.

The multi-actor approach of BioRural requires a participatory ‘bottom-up approach’, facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. Taking a ‘bottom-up’ approach to development allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation. Interactive innovation is a social process rather than a ‘top-down’ scientific approach. Multi actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and codesign practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems.

The process of interactive innovation followed by BioRural will involve the characteristic scenarios, shown in Figure 5¹. These range from engaging and incentivising actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, to applying new knowledge on the ground.

¹ <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 5: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

For each of the above mentioned 6 key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have already been tested during the proposal stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritisation of the identified stakeholders’ groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritisation has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that BioRural aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders’ groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritisation process is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Prioritisation of stakeholders

Other tools that will be used for engaging stakeholders throughout the project implementation refer to understanding stakeholders and registering² their needs with service design methods such as Personas.

Scenario 2: EXAMINING

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used for understanding the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences. Journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATING

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised. The tool has been used during project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation. TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

The tool has been used during project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans. The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

² <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/personas>

Multi-actor approach & DEC actions

The project's multi-actor approach will extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partner's languages;
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end user;
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society, and government;
- Capitalizing on partners existing connections, networks, and events program;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs.

Material will be translated into the languages of the partner countries and the responsibility has already been assigned to specific partners (See Table 2).

Table 2: Translation task among partners

Partner		Language	
	NL		
	FR		
	DE		
	DK		
	PL		
	LT		
	LV		
	ES		
	PT		
	IT		
	GR		
	SI		
	RO		
	MK		

2.4 Target groups

Defining the project's target audience is a critical step for focusing objectives and pursuing meaningful impact.

A clear understanding of the target audiences (e.g., who they are, where they are, what are their needs and their typical characteristics) is an essential part of an effective DEC plan. This is needed to ensure that communication and dissemination channels, as well as the planned and undertaken activities are maximizing

and extending the reach of the project results. This chapter presents the seven target groups that have been identified explaining the benefits they gain through their engagement to the project (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Target groups and respective benefits

2.5 Key messages

Key messages will be used to articulate in a simple straightforward manner the unique benefit of engaging with BioRural. Specific key messages have been identified depending on the communication channel and tool selected.

Arising from the concepts previously mentioned, a set of “backbone” messages per target group have been defined, as the basis for a deeper approach, while aiming to highlight the advantages provided by BioRural. The following table presents the key messages per target group.

Table 3: Target audience, objectives & key messages

Target audience (WHO)	Communication objectives (WHY)	Communication Key messages (WHAT)
Bio-based raw material producers & industries	Long term competitiveness, linkages with bio-based industries, support for scaling. Improved access to renewable raw materials, direct support for scaling, rural job security and satisfaction.	“BioRural can add value to your business by connecting you with bioeconomy innovators and stakeholders. Discover trends and needs of the industry, enter new markets and expand network with end users, researchers and policy makers.”
Rural /urban citizens	Local ownership and economic opportunities, local redevelopment, increased environmental awareness, better quality of life, access to sustainable products	“Find out how bioeconomy and biobased practices and innovations can benefit your daily personal and professional life by getting to know BioRural project.”
Government, policy makers etc.	Knowledge on Bioeconomy and, realization of its multiple benefits, receive policy recommendations,	“Align with BioRural and get support in the design of policies towards innovation adoption and the diffusion

	support local redevelopment and resilience	of bio-based solutions in rural area in order to strengthen them, and to receive benefit nation-wide.”
Local rural schools, universities etc.	Growing environmental awareness, focus on inter- and transdisciplinary research, hands-on knowledge on Bioeconomy applications	“Contribute to the identification of latest technologies in bio-based solutions and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations with other academia stakeholders across Europe.”
NGOs, environmental groups, citizen groups, think tanks	Platform for sharing ideas, knowledge and capacity, access to practical and scientific Bioeconomy knowledge	“Join BioRural networks and gain knowledge and tools for the adoption of circular bio-based proven solutions supporting the development of the wider circular bioeconomy.”
Private sector, Bioeconomy unions/projects	Sustainable business activities, access to sustainable raw materials, multi-actor partnerships, and improved impacts	“Be at the forefront of Bioeconomy developments and take advantage of opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.”

Specific communication tools and channels have been scheduled to reach the identified target groups:

Table 4: Communication tools and channels for target audience Channels, tools, and activities

Communication tools and channels	Bio-based raw material producers	Bio-based industries	Rural /urban citizens	Government, policy makers etc.	Local rural schools, universities etc.	NGOs, group, citizen groups, think tanks	Private sector, Bioeconomy unions/projects
Website & social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E-newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press outreach	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Interviews and outreach videos	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Networking, synergies & liaison activities				✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific, industry and policy publications	✓	✓		✓	✓		

3 Channels, tools and activities

This chapter outlines the communication tools and channels that will be used to connect with the BioRural target groups.

3.1 Visual identity

To target the broadest possible audience, BioRural has created a strong, memorable brand that visually reflects the unique identity and objectives of the project. BioRural will exploit multiple digital platforms to share updates and results and to facilitate ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. Posts, and other inputs will be curated to the target audiences at a frequency that demonstrates consistency and accessibility.

3.1.1 Visual identity and moto

The visual identity is the visible representation of the project. A strong visual identity combines images, colours, and shapes to create a powerful, memorable message to the viewer. BioRural 's visual identity was created considering the following:

- ✓ **Simplicity:** The selected visual identity must be able to tell the story in a simple manner.
- ✓ **Relevance:** An appropriate aesthetic that can be easily correlated with the project objectives.
- ✓ **Uniqueness:** The elements selected must lead to the design of a recognisable and unique visual identity.
- ✓ **Versatility:** A logo that can be easily used in different communication channels (digital and printed).

The logo will be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. Eight logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex A). The most frequently used logo for the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below:

Figure 8: BioRural logo

3.1.2 The use of the EU emblem

BioRural's deliverables will follow the requirements set out by the European Commission and will include the EU flag and the source of funding as follows.

Figure 9: EU Emblem

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages.³

3.1.3 Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”⁴

3.1.4 Colour palette

The colour palette was selected to represent the project’s values. The colours are optimized for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is high enough for black and white printing. The projects brand book is provided in Annex H.

Figure 10: BioRural colour palette

3.1.5 Templates

BioRural will be presented in numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results. A presentation template (ppt) has been designed in line with the BioRural’s graphic identity to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/

⁴ Based on the Annotated Model Grant Agreement: [V0.2 DRAFT– 30.11.2021](#). For any changes, the DEC plan will be updated accordingly.

Figure 11: BioRural presentations template

The BioRural deliverable template is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number, and title) as well as the author's details.

Figure 12: BioRural deliverable template

3.2 BioRural channel mix

3.2.1 Website

The BioRural website has been developed while the landing page of the website has been released on M2. The project's website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BioRural's stakeholders' access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added-value and the impact of bio-based solutions in rural areas. The site will be regularly updated with contributions from all partners. It will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. Finally, the website is mobile friendly, increasing accessibility and maximizing the impact of the project.

Figure 13: BioRural website

BioRural's website has a twofold role as it will serve as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, documents for download and enabling access to the project's social media accounts, and it will also act as a resource centre for research on topics related to biobased solutions and innovations mainly for rural areas, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3, the BioRural website is hosted at www.biorural.eu and will contain the following sections and features.

Home/Landing page

The section includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube), a button for sign-up in the BioRural's newsletter and navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project.

The Project

The section includes a project description as well as description of the project objectives.

Meet our partners

The section includes a list of the consortium partners with active links to their websites.

Success stories

The section includes a presentation of the success cases gathered throughout the project duration. Initially, the section will include the 8 success cases that were originally selected and progressively enriched with the additional ones that partners will identify throughout the project duration.

Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)

The section includes a presentation of the Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) and the 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) as well as registration process for users to join the Networks.

Our Toolkit

The section includes a presentation of the BioRural toolkit which is an online repository of bio-based solutions that enables the interaction between rural actors and provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions. The toolkit will be hosted by a different website, but the BioRural webpage will provide direct access.

Newsroom

Press releases and posts will be the main content of this section and will inform stakeholders of all project's activities and upcoming events.

Resources

The section will include posters, brochures, project factsheets, notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners, stickers, video covers and a printable brand book and guideline.

Resources

The section will include two submenus:

- a) **Deliverables:** Providing links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo.
- b) **Media kit:** Providing access to all the project communication material (e.g., brochure, banner, deliverable template).

Get in Touch

All the contact information of the BioRural project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with the project's stakeholders.

3.2.2 Digital and printed outreach

3.2.2.1 Social media

The project aims to have a strong social media presence and establish two-way communication channels, to better reach and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, five (5) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

- The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups;
- The most adequate, valid, and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders; and
- The most popular social media platforms to communicate and interact with various stakeholders.

BioRural is already registered and active on the following five social media platforms:

Figure 14: BioRural's social media

The social media described above have been selected to further enhance the multi-actor approach of the project. Different kind of stakeholders require different means of approach. In that sense, the following characteristics have been taken into account:

- **Facebook:** This channel is used mainly for building relationships and keeping contact with peers and contacts. It is a good platform for building loyalty of the existing network base. Because of the plain language and messages, the content can reach out to several target groups regardless of social and business backgrounds. BioRural will use this channel to reach biobased professionals, rural /urban citizens, training institutions, NGOs, citizen groups, think tanks by sharing any project and partner news and updates.
- **Twitter:** This channel is used mainly for building awareness and enhancing public relations. Twitter is also often used to provide real time updates. BioRural will use this channel to reach regional or national governmental bodies, policy makers, research institutions, NGOs and media actors by giving focus on workshops and events that will be happening throughout its course.
- **LinkedIn:** This channel is used mainly for creating awareness and generating networking and collaboration opportunities due to its professional character and style of communication. BioRural will use this channel to reach Bio-based innovators and professionals, Bioeconomy experts, think-tanks and other relevant stakeholders by promoting the creation of the ERBN and sharing updates about project key activities.
- **YouTube:** This channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes due to its character and features. BioRural will use this channel to reach any stakeholder interested in Bioeconomy by promoting the testimonial videos on the identified success cases, interviews, and outreach videos.
- **SlideShare:** This channel is mainly used for communication and education purposes. Project presentations will be uploaded for easy access to anyone interested.

To maximize visibility and impact of the project's events and outcomes, BioRural will exploit the consortium's already developed social media networks. This means that partners are expected to share, publish, and retweet content from BioRural's social media accounts and website, which will increase traction for project-related work and increase traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels.

After selecting the most appropriate channels there are several parameters to consider when the consortium will create social media content:

- ✓ **Interactivity** is the main pillar of the generated content and is the best way to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by non-specialists to facilitate interaction.
- ✓ **Eye-catching** posts will lead to higher conversions with prioritization into visuals and graphics will make the piece unique.
- ✓ **Adaptability** of the social media assets to the format and functionality of the several devices. The asset will be used in such a frame to maximize their placement, especially taking into consideration the placement on mobile devices.

#Hashtags

Creating hashtags that are relevant to the project and its outcomes will help reach target audiences and make it easy to find BioRural generated knowledge. Hashtags divide the project’s main topics into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and will help increase visibility in the social media environment, while they will make our messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Further tracking of the hashtags is going to help the consortium to analyze quantitative and qualitative data.

The project has set official distinctive hashtags such a **#BioRural**, **#Bioeconomy**, **#Rural**, **#circular**, **#biobasedinnovations** which are used to monitor the posts related to the project.

LinkedIn

A LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/biorural/>) was created to network with the BioRural target audiences and promote the project’s activities.

As such, all the project’s news will be published on its LinkedIn profile and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes to attract a wider audience. Figure 15 provides an overview of BioRural’s LinkedIn profile.

Figure 15: BioRural LinkedIn profile

Facebook

BioRural’s Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/bioruraleu>) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level. Figure 16 provides an overview of BioRural’s Facebook profile.

Figure 16: BioRural Facebook profile

Twitter

A Twitter account was created (https://twitter.com/bio_rural) to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policy makers and advisors. BioRural will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them, and post news, events, and updates on the project’s status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect to ‘high influencers’ in the research and business topics of the BioRural project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 17: BioRural Twitter profile

SlideShare

A SlideShare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/BioRural>) has been created to present project material in an engaging visual format that appeals to BioRural’s audience. Project presentations will be available for any interested stakeholder providing key information on the project implementation and activities.

Figure 18: BioRural SlideShare page

YouTube

YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@biorural>) will be used to host and promote the BioRural videos, which will be of wide variety, such as interviews, promotional and outreach videos.

Figure 19: BioRural YouTube page

3.2.2.2 Brochure

Brochures will be distributed at the project’s events (regional and National workshops, European Contest) as well as relevant events where the project can be promoted, to provide concise project information relevant to the target groups. A 3-fold brochure has been designed for this purpose and is presented below (Figure 20) as well as in Annex C. Partners will translate the brochure into project’s languages.

Figure 20: BioRural Brochure sides A&B

3.2.2.3 Banner

Banners will be used at physical events for eye-catching identification of the BioRural booth. Two versions of the banner have been created, with the latest to include the project’s social media as well as a QR code leading to the project website providing direct access to the project’s scope and activities. BioRural banner is presented in Figure 21 and Annex C. The banner will be translated to all consortium partners’ languages.

Figure 21: BioRural Banner

3.2.3 Multiplier campaigns

3.2.3.1 Newsletter

An electronic newsletter will be published to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This will include the latest developments and activities as well as upcoming events and workshops as well as where to find recent reports and publications.

Subscription to the newsletter will be made through the project’s website. For the development of the newsletters a MailChimp account will be created by FSH.

BioRural will pay special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users’ personal data and newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to receiving any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European and international legal framework, and the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BioRural Newsletter and all the collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner’s servers. These data will not be accessible from other third parties. More detailed description of how these data will be collected, stored, and handled will be presented in the

respective deliverables (D6.3 Data Management Plan, D6.4 Data Management Plan 1st update). To achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, the BioRural partners will be encouraged to promote the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

The first draft of the newsletter will be produced by FSH, with content provided by partners and it will be sent to all consortium partners for review after its completion. The partners will provide their feedback and then FSH will publish the newsletter and promote it to all social media accounts of the project. All newsletters will be uploaded and remain available on the project’s website.

Newsletters will be published every six months (January, June) and anticipate more than 500 subscriptions over the course of the project.

The proposed structure of each newsletter is:

- Introduction
- Project Update / News & Events
- Resources for further reading (if available)

3.2.3.2 Press releases

Press releases will be carried out by partners to provide information about the key activities implemented and to share important updates related to project milestones such as the launch of the BioRural Toolkit, the creation of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network etc. The table below presents the indicative planning of the press releases based on the achieved milestones and tasks throughout the course of the project. The month of release may change based on the progress of the project implementation.

Table 5: Press releases planning

Month	Scope of press release
M2	linked to the project kick off (Milestone 1)
M12	linked to the creation of the ERBN (Milestone 2)
M13	linked to key results of the report "Stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests" (Task 1.3)
M14	linked to the launch of the toolkit (Milestone 7)
M27	linked to the completion of RBP workshops (Milestone 5)
M32	linked to the European bioeconomy challenge (Milestone 6)
M34	linked to the identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform (Task 2.4)
M35	linked to the completion of the business model blueprints
M36	linked to the Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development (Task 3.4)

To maximize influence on local stakeholders, the consortium will translate all press releases into all consortium partners’ languages (14 in total). A press release template has been developed (Annex C) and shared with partners.

The first press release has been created and distributed to the partners for translation and circulation to local/regional media. Relevant screenshots of the press release published in several local media outlets are presented below:

Figure 22: Press release in Greek media

Figure 23: Press release in NMK media

3.2.3.3 Interviews

Interviews in radio and TV will maximize the visibility of the project activities and reach to target audience that is not familiar with other digital channels such as the website and social media. The interviews will be focused on the promotion of key activities of the project (e.g., success stories, creation of the ERBN) and will be mainly targeted to the general public as well as bioeconomy actors (farmers, fishermen/women, foresters etc.).

3.2.3.4 Promotional videos

The Biorural consortium will develop marketing-style videos promoting the project's success stories as well as the innovators behind them. The first eight success stories are presented in the table below. The list will be further enriched with the course of the project and the identification of additional success stories by the partners (M10-M36). In total **20 promotional videos** will be produced.

Table 6: Success stories to be promoted

Partner	Success story
	“Bio-based Garden” success story
	“Bioplastics” success story
Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation State Research Institute	“Pustelnia” success story
	“Latvia’s State Forests” success story
Spanish Biom Association	“Gasification and Biochar from olive waste” success story
CHALLENGE FOR BIOECONOMY WATER & ENERGY	“SCIVEN” success story
InCommOn Innovative Communication Services	“Staramaki” success story
algen Algal Technology Centre	“Algae production” success story

3.2.3.5 Podcast series

Podcasts are digital audio files presented in a series, typically with new instalments received automatically by subscribers. This on-demand technology is growing in popularity with listener penetration expected to reach or exceed 30% across Europe by 2030 according to recent data.

BioRural will create 2 podcast series of ten episodes in total, to enrich and diversify the website and address auditory learning styles. Content created by partners will follow an overarching theme that will make for cohesive, entertaining series. The length of each episode will be around 15-20 minutes. The series will be available for free on Google Podcasts.

The two podcast categories will focus on the following categories:

- Commercial bio-based solutions & financing tools
- Capacity building on Bioeconomy including participating ideas of the European Bioeconomy Challenge

The podcast series will be developed during months 24-36.

3.2.4 Publications

BioRural foresees the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts to influence a wide range of targeted stakeholders and to promote the project and its findings. All publications will implement Open Access and open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

- far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- high likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

Scientific publications

For the scientific publications, the consortium will apply the Open Access Policy as described in OpenAIRE (<http://www.openaire.eu/>). More specifically, partners will deposit scientific peer-reviewed publications in a centralized repository. Generally, BioRural will conform to the EC Open Access mandates: as a minimum, all publications will be available via Green Open Access, e.g., OpenAIRE, ResearchGate and repositories supported by individual institutions and when possible, Gold Open Access will be selected, using project and own funding contributions.

BioRural will strive to publish at least 3 peer reviewed scientific papers in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project’s results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project’s work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners (CERTH, AU, VDU, LLU, UC, UL) and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the BioRural project.

Industry publications

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, BioRural aims to publish at least 15 featured articles in high-quality industry magazines, to make the project and its results known to the industrial stakeholders. To maximize impact, steps and timing for identifying, selecting, and producing publications have been defined:

Figure 24: BioRural steps for article submission

Policy Guideline Report

To increase the uptake and the promotion of the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas, a comprehensive set of policy measures is required. More specifically through the success stories and the advancements of the project, the consortium aims to formulate recommendations to identify new growth opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors and foster interactions with and between EC services and other related national/international initiatives. Consulting with EC actors (i.e., DG AGRI, DG ENER, DG CLIMA, DG GROW, DG RTD, DG ENV, DG JRC) will optimise the developed Policy Guidelines and maximize their impact.

Findings will be translated into 2 policy reports (one joined policy brief will be developed in collaboration with the other three projects from the same topic and one policy guideline report), increasing the share of Bioeconomy value in rural areas.

White paper

One white paper will be published to translate BioRural results into usable evidence for policy makers that draws from scientific data and stakeholder input. The publication will inform policy makers about the results and impacts of governance model adoption in view of future policy design and help shape public policy and future regulations in the field of bioeconomy.

Practice Abstracts

BioRural will produce 30 practice abstracts in the EIP Agri format dedicated to the project’s activities and outcomes. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/ recommendation/ practice regarding the deployment of biobased solutions that can be used by the end-users to enhance circular economy and bioeconomy in the rural areas. The innovative knowledge and end-user material delivered by the project will feed into the EIP-AGRI website for wider dissemination (T5.2).

3.2.5 Event planning

Event planning will take part in two phases. On a 6-month basis an event planning form will be sent to the partners to describe the events that are already in their calendars (Annex D). A brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for BioRural (i.e., workshop, booth) will support the decision-making process. This form has been sent to partners, and the responses will be compiled using an online reporting tool (Table 7) for easy reference and record keeping.

Table 7: BioRural’s event participation template

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

Several potential events have already been identified as presented in the following table.

Table 8: Potential events for participation

#	Partner	Event	Date	Location	Target groups	Potential involvement
1	FSH	Annual International Symposium on Agricultural Research	10-13/07/2023	Athens, Greece	Researchers	Publication, poster, banner
2	FSH	Agrotica	October 2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Private sector, Agri-rural communities	Workshop, seminar, booth

3	VAL	CFIA Rennes	14-16/03/2023	Rennes, France	Agri-food sector	Brochure / project factsheet
5	VDU	Cannabis Hub.LT 2022	11-12/11/2022	Kaunas, Lithuania	Bio-based raw material producers Bio-based industries	
6	ICO	Mentoring workshop	November- December 2022	Lesbos & Edessa, Greece	Rural and urban citizens, NGOs	Brochure, Invitation to RBP/ERBN, Mention of workshops and EU Challenge
7	AVE	Innovative practices for bioeconomy- Expobiomasa (Valladolid trade fair)	9-11 May 2023	Valladolid	Bioeconomy pymes; researchers; consultants; rural organisations	Co-organising; 30min to 1 hour time slot
8	AVE	BIORURAL in EXPOBIOMASA fair	9-11 May 2023	Valladolid	Fair attendants	Roll-up and info point at AVEBIOM stand
9	AVE	BIORURAL in Salon del gas Renovable fair	Oct 2023	Valladolid	Fair attendants	Roll-up and info point at AVEBIOM room
10	Delphy	World Bio Markets	10-11 May 2023	The Netherlands	bio developers and producers, global brands and buyers, investors and financiers, suppliers and community enablers.	Info point, brochure / project factsheet

To better coordinate efforts between partners participating at similar events and establish an effective plan for BioRural, information will be consolidated online in a living document that will be updated frequently.

The second phase involves the selection of events. This will be done based upon the guidelines below. These necessary actions and when they should occur will ensure event participation aligns with the project's

objectives and budget. These will need to be adapted to individual activities, since numerous factors can result in varying steps and deadlines.

Figure 25: Guidelines for event selection and planning

3.2.6 Networking and synergies

Building synergies and expanding the BioRural ecosystem is a significant priority of the DEC plan. Much of the project’s work will build upon the experience, knowledge and/or data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach will be extended to the DEC and will involve a three-step process.

Phase 1: Identification

Potentially mutually beneficial partnerships and synergies will first be identified, building from the list provided in the template in Table 9.

Table 9: BioRural’s synergy & liaison mapping template

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

The template has been sent to partners requesting information on any other project’s/networks or initiatives they are currently participating in that could be relevant to BioRural. This template will be revised every 6 months to add new projects.

A preliminary list is included in Table 10. BioRural will consider both projects that are near completion and those that run in parallel. Connecting with projects that will be ending, will provide networking opportunities for BioRural. Projects, networks, and initiatives running in parallel will provide several opportunities to strengthen communication pathways and conduct joint activities.

Table 10: Preliminary list of potential project and initiative synergies

Ongoing or nearing completion Projects

	AgroFossilFree	https://www.agrofossilfree.eu/
	BIOEASTsUP	https://bioeast.eu/bioeastsup/
	BioeconomyVentures	https://www.bioeconomyventures.eu/
	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/
	BRANCHES	https://www.branchesproject.eu/
	AgroBioHeat	https://agrobioheat.eu/
	AgroRES	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/agrores/
	BIOMASUD PLUS	http://biomasudplus.eu/en_GB/
	SecureChain	http://www.securechain.eu/
	BIOFIT	https://www.biofit-h2020.eu/
	BE-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/
	BIOSWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/
	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/
	MPowerBIO	https://mpowerbio.eu/
	ReNu2Farm	https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/renu2farm-nutrient-recycling-from-pilot-production-to-farms-and-fields/
	RELIEF	https://relief.uop.gr/
	IndiGo	https://indigo-interregproject.eu/en/
	Biomodel4region	https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/
	FoodLevers	https://www.foodlevers.org/
	CEE2ACT	https://www.cee2act.eu/
	ENOUGH	https://enough-emissions.eu/
	POSHMyCo	https://www.google.com/url?q=http://www.poshmyco.eu/&sa=D&source=editors&ust=1667831625208895&usg=AOvVaw1AoYbnpNRhv8eG4ESngdvb
	FIRE-RES	https://fire-res.eu/
	ParAqua	https://paraqua-cost.eu/
	BRANCHES	https://www.branchesproject.eu/

Project recently funded under Horizon Europe (boost circular bioeconomy and bioeconomy sectors)		
MainstreamBIO		
RuralBioUp		
SCALE-UP		
BIOTRANSFORM		
Project recently funded under Horizon Europe (governance perspective)		
ShapingBio		
BIOMODEL4REGIONS		
BIOLOC		
BBC		
BlueRev		
RefreSCAR		
Other Initiatives and Networks		
	European Bioeconomy Network	https://eubionet.eu/ (BioRural is already member of the Network)
	Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)	https://www.bbi.europa.eu/
	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy_en
	HUB Bioéconomie working group	https://www.paysdelaloire.fr/mon-conseil-regional/les-missions-regionales/europe/le-hub-bioeconomie
	Transform4Europe	http://www.transform4europe.eu/
	Lithuanian Green Alliance (lit. Lietuvos žaliasis aljansas)	https://www.lzajansas.lt/lt/naujienos/
	Association for European Life Science Universities (ICA)	https://www.ica-europe.info/
	National AKIS cluster	https://zua.vdu.lt/en/zemes-ukio-ziniu-ir-inovaciju-sistemas-klasteris/
	Smart Waste Portugal - Business Development Network	http://www.smartwasteportugal.com/pt/
	Dueceira - Associação de Desenvolvimento do Ceira e Dueça	https://dueceira.pt/
	Rede Rural Nacional	https://www.rederural.gov.pt/

	Green Ideas Greece competition	https://greenideasgreece.org/
	Balkan Green Ideas competition	https://www.balkangreenideas.org/
	Algae 4 Wastewater working group	https://www.eaba-association.org/en/working-groups

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure synergies will benefit the project and align with BioRural’s objectives, each potential project, initiatives, and network will be assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance;
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value);
- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources);
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation will be consolidated with the information provided by partners and a final decision will be made by the consortium.

Phase 3: Contact

Once it has been agreed upon that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact will be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities will be decided after discussions with their representatives and the BioRural consortium and will include (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities;
- Joint policy events;
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications;
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs;
- Participation in the other’s events & networks;
- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

All the project’s templates have been uploaded by FSH to the project’s Google Drive folder that has been created, providing direct and continuous access to partners for updating reasons.

3.2.7 EC tools

BioRural will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project’s results.

Figure 26: EC Tools

4 Monitoring and evaluation

4.1 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are concrete, measurable targets used for monitoring and evaluating the project's progress and enabling adaptation when necessary. A set of dissemination and communication KPIs and targets have been identified and are presented in the following tables:

Table 11: Dissemination KPIs

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D1	Project events	
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5
D2	Scientific publications	
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15
D3	ERBN	
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	1000
D4	Synergies	
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5
D5	Policy guidelines	
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>5

Table 12: Communication KPIs

#	Communication KPIs	Target
C1	Branding & material	
C1.1	Visual identity	1
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1
C1.3	Website	1
C1.4	Social media channels	5
C1.5	Flyers	4000
C1.6	Banners	15
C2	Digital outreach	
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000
C2.2	Blog posts	60
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000

C3	Multiplier campaigns	
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500
C3.2	Press releases	9
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10

Furthermore, the KPIs have been distributed between the three years in which the DEC plan will be also updated.

Table 13: Dissemination KPIs per Year

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
D1	Project events				
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5		5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42		42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4		4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	1	7	3
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	1	3	2
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5		3	5
D2	Scientific publications				
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3			3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15		6	10
D3	ERBN				
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5			6
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5		2	5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5			6
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1			1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000			
D4	Synergies				
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15		9	10
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4			5
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5		3	3
D5	Policy guidelines				
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1			2
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1			2

Table 14: Communication KPIs per Year

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
C1	Branding & material				
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1		
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1		
C1.3	Website	1	1		
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5		

D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000		
C1.6	Banners	15	15		
C2	Digital outreach				
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	10	21	29
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	135	195	175
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5	5		
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000			
C3	Multiplier campaigns				
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500			
C3.2	Press releases	9	1	4	4
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	2	9	
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	8		12
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10			10

Moreover, to effectively share the responsibility for spreading project results and maximizing the impact derived from partners' expertise, experience, and networks, KPIs and targets have been assigned to each partner as presented in the following tables:

Table 15: Dissemination KPIs per partner

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
D1	Project events																					
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop	5	5	•			•		•	•		•		•				•	•			•
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42	42	1	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3	3		3	1	1		3	3	3
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4	4	•	•					•		•	•									
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	11	4						2	2	1		1					1			
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	6	2						1		1		1					1			
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5	8	1	1	1				1	1	1		1					1			
D2	Scientific publications																					
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3	3						1	1	1											
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15	16			2	1						4		1	1	4			1	1	1
D3	ERBN																					
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5	6	1	1	1							1			1						1
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5	7	1					1	1	1	1		1					1			
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5	6	1		1							1			1						1
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1	1														1					
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000	10000																			
D4	Synergies																					
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15	17	4		4				2			3			2	2					
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4	5	1		1				1			1			1						
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5	6	2	1					1			1					1				
D5	Policy guidelines																					
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1	2	2																		
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1	2							1	1											

Table 16: Communication KPIs per partnerr

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
C1	Branding & material																					
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1														1					
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1														1					
C1.3	Website	1	1														1					
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5														5					
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000	450	200	200		200	200	300	200	300	300	200		200	450	200		200	200	200
C1.6	Banners	15	15														15					
C2	Digital outreach																					
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000	0																			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	60	8	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	6	2	2	2	11	6	2	2	2	2
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	505	50	20	20	20	20	20	10	20	20	30	20	20	20	85	50	20	20	20	20
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000	1100																			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	5	5														5					
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000	2000														2000					
C3	Multiplier campaigns																					
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500	505																			
C3.2	Press releases	9	9	1						1	1		1				2	1	2			
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	11	1	1		1			1		1	1		1		2	1		1		
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	20	2	2		2			2		2	2		2		2	2		2		
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10	10														10					

4.2 Reporting tools

Event and communication reporting

Partners will be asked to report on their dissemination and communications activities monthly. Feedback will be collected from partners using an online form with two key categories:

- i) **Events and Activities**
- ii) **Other Communication Actions**

The screenshot shows a Google Form with the BioRural logo at the top. The title is "BioRural Event, Activity and Communication Reporting". The text inside the form reads: "Dear BioRural partners, This form will be used for reporting all activities and events organized or attended by the BioRural consortium members as well as communication channels engaged by the consortium members on a monthly basis. You are kindly requested to fill in the relevant information prior to the monthly consortium meeting so we may update the website and social media in a timely manner. Information will also be used to track KPIs and ensure we are meeting them. Sincerely, Foodscale Hub Team".

Figure 27: Google forms for collecting partner information regarding events and communication

Input from the partners will be consolidated and used to monitor DEC progress and make necessary adjustments to the plan, and to hold partners accountable. All consolidated information will be hosted in the project's Google Drive.

Table 17: Form for consolidating partner input regarding events participation

BioRural Event Participation consolidating list							
#	Partner	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	BioRural involvement

Table 18: Form used for tracking partner's communication activities

BioRural communication activities consolidating list						
#	Partner	Type of activity	Date	Target groups	Relative link (if available)	Additional info

5 Exploitation & IPR management

BioRural will produce several commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This chapter provides a presentation of these results, potential pathways for their exploitation and IPRs related to them as identified until M3. Further analysis on the Exploitation strategy will be developed by M18 with D5.2 and M36 with D5.3 to expand upon this initial plan and provide a concrete roadmap for the duration of the project and beyond.

5.1 Exploitation pathways

Each KER requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type and whether it can be commercialized. A description of the KERs, their target groups and the unique value they offer are described in this section as well as potential exploitation pathways for commercial and non-commercial results.

BioRural has identified 4 key exploitable results (KERs) that will be available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders. Tables 19-22 describe each result, scope of exploitation, UVP, target groups and scope/ means of exploitation.

All partners provided their feedback by answering an online table - tailor made to BioRural's exploitation and IPR validation (Annex I).

Table 19: ERBN- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: European Rural Bioeconomy Network	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Four regional RBPs will be formed by splitting Europe in 4 quartiles (NW, NE, SW and SE) to connect neighboring countries and identify commonalities to impose members' connection and ensure sustainability. The 4 RBPs will constitute the ERBN. All partners will locate, make connections and develop synergies with Bioeconomy actors to stimulate knowledge exchange, cooperation and collaboration and assist on developing future rural Bioeconomy initiatives. Each RBP will be led by one partner (NW:DELPHY, NE: IUNG, SW: AVE and SE: CERTH) to ensure the process continuation during the project.
Unique Value Proposition	Creation of a Network of more than 400 members from various sectors including primary sector, Academia, Public Authorities, Industry, Consultants etc. joining forces to boost Bioeconomy in rural areas.
Target groups	Scientific Community, Policy makers, Industry, Society-Citizens, NGOs, environmental groups, think tanks, any other key actor in knowledge transfer" (or any key actor in the national AKIS system)
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial & Commercial
Means of exploitation	<u>Non-commercial</u> The exploitation will derive from the diffusion of knowledge. The ERBN members will be invited to participate in national and regional workshops on knowledge exchange and capacity building (WP3) aimed at directly supporting them in developing and scaling rural bio-based solutions. Scientific exploitation is based on the diffusion of hands-on knowledge on Bioeconomy applications and solutions circulated within the scientific community that will participate in the ERBN. The scientific community can exploit the outcomes and the collected data for further research advancements in the Bioeconomy domain. Policy making exploitation is based on policy recommendations and increased awareness on Bioeconomy development and support interaction of policy makers from different countries and rural areas.

	<p>Commercial exploitation The network will facilitate collaboration between stakeholders (for instance primary producers and processors) through providing them with a platform to initiate contact and sharing of information.</p>
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Table 20: Toolkit- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: BioRural Toolkit	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	The Toolkit will integrate various levels of information (e.g., scientific publications & reports, policy guidelines, legislation) and make it available to small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.
Unique Value Proposition	An effective, all-encompassing BioRural Toolkit with an enhanced repository of up-to-date Bioeconomy data.
Target groups	Innovators, Rural areas' actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial
Means of exploitation	<p>The exploitation of the KER will derive from the diffusion of knowledge related to various sources such as scientific papers and reports, research projects, policy guidelines, legislation and financing or in-kind initiatives related to bio-based solutions for rural areas.</p> <p>Scientific exploitation is related to the scientific and research papers that will be available within the Toolkit. Scientific community can exploit the outcomes and the collected data for further research advancements in the Bioeconomy domain. Examples from the project include two types of questionnaires (for end-users and experts) for identifying stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests; the data on structural characteristics of rural small businesses population that will participate in the systematic end-users survey; and national and regional (across four RBP) findings from the survey providing an overview of stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests about bio-based solutions for rural areas. The country factsheets to be created under T1.1 and findings from the survey will provide an overview of stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests about bio-based solutions for rural areas.</p> <p>Policy making exploitation is related to the availability of policy recommendations & white papers within the Toolkit. EU, regional and national policy makers can utilize the project's data and results (that will be also deposited to the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy), enhancing the development of evidence-based Bioeconomy policies.</p> <p>Training exploitation is related to the training material & video tutorials of the online Bioeconomy workshops, that will be available within the Toolkit to citizens, NGOs and other interested groups.</p>

Table 21: Business models - Key Exploitable Result

KER name: Bio-based business models	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Business model blueprints for each of the 5 selected Bioeconomy themes will be developed in order to support the development of successful bio-economy businesses for future innovative bio-based rural regions. The final

	outcome will be a highly reusable set of tools and methods that can accelerate the adoption of circular business models in rural communities in a tangible way.
Unique Value Proposition	Tailored to the Bioeconomy domain business models, designed to match the specific needs of rural stakeholders, while incorporating critical technology, business and societal aspects.
Target groups	Innovators, Rural areas' actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level
Scope of exploitation	Commercial
Means of exploitation	The business model blueprints will be publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit and will assist stakeholders in forming their individual circular business models with the support of the business experts of the consortium Commercial exploitation: The blueprints will allow stakeholders to produce either regional Bioeconomy development models with emphasis on the specific bio-based solutions suitable for the local environment or private business plans for new ideas (from inception) and existing solutions (at any stage) that require a Bioeconomy upgrade.

Table 22: Policy Guidelines - Key Exploitable Result

KER name: Policy Guidelines	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Guidelines on: (i) interactive and multi-actor innovation processes specific to bio-based solutions for rural areas; (ii) new funding formats enhancing innovation-driven research about bio-based solutions; (iii) future research; iv) topics of interest for the nationals and EU research agendas (including further HE programming); (v) fostering a better targeted and shared research agenda on innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects.
Unique Value Proposition	Supporting Bioeconomy development, considering the selected themes and involved regions' specificities. Legislative barriers will be mitigated by developing policy guidelines that feedback into the development of the circular rural Bioeconomy.
Target groups	Policy makers , National & regional government officials
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial
Means of exploitation	The policy guidelines will be publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit as well as via Zenodo that will be uploaded upon their completion. Policy making exploitation: Policy guidelines will consist of research and policy recommendations and produce crisp and focused policy briefs with key messages easily and quickly grasped by the target groups. EU, regional and national policy makers can utilize the project's policy guidelines, enhancing the development of evidence-based Bioeconomy policies.

The following table presents the KERs associated with the partners involved in their exploitation according to the identification process made during DEC preparation.

Table 23: Identified KERs & involved partners

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Partners involved in KERs exploitation																		
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Toolkit	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	Business model blueprints	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
4	Policy Guidelines	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓					✓			

All BioRural’s currently identified KERs will be openly accessible and available free of charge during the project’s lifetime. After the project’s completion the BioRural Toolkit and ERBN will be further developed by all partners ensuring the reuse of assets by the Bioeconomy community.

In particular, the further development of the **BioRural Toolkit** and enrichment with relevant Bioeconomy data including scientific research, projects and initiatives, success stories and funding opportunities, will be undertaken mainly by the scientific partners. In this light, it will become freely and openly available through a vast network of relevant stakeholders and the general public. The benefits are twofold:

- ensure that key stakeholders and end-users have continuous access to the platform and its innovative tools.
- get immediate access to new validated data that will continuously populate the Toolkit.

The post project sustainability of the **BioRural network** beyond EC funding will be addressed thoroughly in a comprehensive **Sustainability plan (D5.3)** that will address the following key aspects of network’s modus operandi, namely:

- Institutional plan:** will cover the legal form, the governance model of the network, the decision-making process, and the conditions for membership. The governance model will be designed under the principles of inclusiveness, openness and expansion;
- Organizational plan:** will define the internal structure of the network, roles, responsibilities, and job descriptions. It will be designed under the principles of efficiency, cost-effectiveness and will aim to support the scale-up potential of the network;
- Financial plan:** will set-up the basis of a dual purpose, sustainability in terms of covering the operational costs of the network and affordability so that rural communities and stakeholders can become members and benefit from network services. While the detailed financial model will be defined in WP5 during project implementation, the basic principle of the financial model will be as follows: Stakeholders that are interested in the services of the Toolkit can become members by subscribing and paying an annual membership fee (with minimum possible pricing). Membership fee will be substantial enough to cover the costs associated with the maintenance of the platform, but at the same time very affordable to the members, even in low-income European countries.

Identification of new KERs- project procedure

As the project progresses additional KERs might be identified by the partners. To this end, certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in the figure below:

Figure 28: Newly identified KERs procedure

The first step towards the identification of a KER by a partner, is for the latter to inform the Coordinator and WP5 leader providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. Specific analysis needs to be made covering the following aspects:

- Scope of exploitation
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation (how)

A relevant form has been developed and shared with the partners during DEC preparation (Annex I).

Once this step is concluded, the above-mentioned form is sent to the consortium and partners are asked to validate the new KER. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new KER is validated, it is included to the project's KERs list mentioned in Table 23.

5.2 IPR strategy

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are the ownership rights for creations of the mind, such as inventions, names, images, or designs and can enable owners to obtain financial benefit from their ideas. Striking the right balance between creator and public interests can foster creativity and innovation.

All KERs are potentially subject to IPR management. D5.7 Bio-Rural network sustainability plan will provide a detailed plan for each result and outline concrete IPR measures to be taken by the partners. BioRural will examine the protection of any result that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited, and if possible, reasonable, and justified, protect them.

5.2.1 Types of IPR⁵

The standard forms of IPR protection include:

⁵ World Intellectual Property Organization. "What is Intellectual Property?" <https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>.

- **Patent:** an exclusive right granted for an invention. It allows the owner to decide how and whether the invention can be used by others
- **Trademark:** a sign that distinguishes goods and services of one enterprise from those of another
- **Industrial design:** includes the aesthetic aspect of an object. 2D features can include patterns, lines, and colours, whereas 3D features extend to shape and surface
- **Copyright:** is the legal term to describe the rights over literary and artistic work but can also extend to databases, advertisement, maps, and technical drawings
- **Trade-secret:** commercially valuable confidential information which may be sold or licensed. This can include technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, lists of customers
- **Confidentiality:** information that is not publicly known and warrants protection

The choice of the most suitable form will be based upon the specifications of the activity and its results.

BioRural will produce significant research results and technological innovations. Hence, a strategy that will handle all IP rights matters will be developed, creating an encouraging environment for further exploitation of the generated discoveries and knowledge. As such, BioRural handles IPR Management on a two-level approach:

During the project: BioRural will give emphasis to the protection of IPRs derived from the project implementation, ensuring that any IPR generated shall rest with the industry that created it and can further exploit it commercially. Under this framework, a set of both protective and supportive measures (such as the obligation to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements) will be undertaken by the consortium to create confidence in all participants. Knowledge Management and democratization of scientific knowledge: The consortium will publish the overall project results through publications, seminars and in the project website, without charging intellectual property rights. Further, partners will deposit scientific peer reviewed publications in a centralized repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the HE “Open science policy”.

Post-Project IPR Strategy: The pre-identified and newly generated IPRs can and will be protected. However, given that BioRural is aiming to support the rural areas, the BioRural Toolkit will be licenced under a copyleft licence (e.g., GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use, and encouraging further knowledge sharing.

The following table presents the IPRs of the four KERs as they were identified by the partners during DEC preparation.

Table 24: BioRural KERs & linked IPRs

KERs		Linked IPRs to the KERs
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	no IPR
2	Toolkit	Copyleft
3	Business model blueprints	no IPR
4	Policy Guidelines	no IPR

Identification of new IPRs- project procedure

As the project progresses additional IPRs might be identified by the partners. To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in the figure below:

Inclusion of newly identified IPRs

Figure 29: Newly identified IPRs procedure

The identification of new IPRs is closely related to the identification process of KERs described above. In that way, when a new KER is identified, the partner follows the same procedure by informing the Coordinator and the WP5 leader on the relative IPR that is linked to the KER as presented in Annex I.

Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new IPR is validated, it is included to the project's IPR list.

5.2.2 Partner obligations

BioRural will follow all IPR management requirements described in the Grant Agreement as well as the signed Consortium Agreement.

Access rights

The beneficiaries must give each other, and the other participants access to the background identified as needed for implementing the action, subject to any specific rules in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

'Background' means any **data, know-how or information** — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and
- needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Grant Agreement.

According to the Consortium Agreement and specifically Article 9, the Parties have identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and have also, where relevant, informed each other that Access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

Results and ownership

'Results' means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.2 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities including but not limited to research contracts in national and European funded projects with third parties provided it does not lead to any commercial or monetary benefit to third parties involved in such cooperative research project on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

The **granting authority** has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notably summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes —during the action or afterwards.

The right to use the beneficiaries' materials, documents and information is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive, and irrevocable licence, which includes the following rights:

- i. use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the granting authority or any other EU service (including institutions, bodies, offices, agencies, etc.) or EU Member State institution or body; copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers; and communication through press information services)
- ii. distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display, or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes)
- iii. editing or redrafting (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (e.g., meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g., audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation)
- iv. translation
- v. storage in paper, electronic or other form
- vi. archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- vii. the right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license to third parties the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f), if needed for the information, communication and publicity activity of the granting authority

If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including intellectual property rights or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned).

The Sustainability plan (D5.3) will include a Results ownership list as per the periodic reporting requirements of the Grant Agreement.

Transfer of results

According to the Consortium Agreement, each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results, including its share in jointly owned Results, following the procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement.

In the case of ownership transfer to the third party, the third party must be identified in Attachment (3) of the Consortium Agreement and the other Parties must waive their right to prior notice and to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement.

The transferring Party must inform the other Parties at the time of transfer and will ensure the rights of other Parties are not affected by such a transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after signing the Consortium Agreement requires a decision of the General Assembly.

Access Rights to Results

Access Rights to Results if needed for exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement.

A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

For the avoidance of doubt any grant of Access Rights not covered by the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement shall be at the absolute discretion of the owning Party and subject to such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the owning and receiving Parties.

Dissemination of Results

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of partner's own results such as publications and presentations, shall be governed by the Grant Agreement.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice.

If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

An objection is justified if the intended publication:

- a) would prevent patenting or other protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background with registrable intellectual property rights or
- b) includes Background, unpublished solely owned Results or Confidential Information of the objecting Party. The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

In addition, the unpublished results or background of any partner will not be used for dissemination purposes without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval.

Access rights for software adhere to the same rules as described above. Access rights do not include source or object code ported to a certain hardware platform or software documentation beyond what is available from the party granting the access rights. The **BioRural Toolkit** will be licensed under a copyleft license (e.g., GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use, and encouraging further knowledge sharing.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary **breaches any of the obligations** of the Grant Agreement (Section 2), the **grant may be reduced**.

Non-disclosure of information

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to any other Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally and has

been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipients hereby undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on non-disclosure under the Grant Agreement, for a period of 5 years after the end of the Project:

- a) not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- b) not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
- c) to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- d) to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

5.2.3 Next steps

At the proposal stage, the **BioRural Toolkit** was identified as a result subject to IPR. As its development progresses a thorough assessment will be undertaken to apply the most appropriate IPR. All newly generated knowledge and results will be recorded and assessed to clearly **determine ownership** and steps will be recommended for seeking proper protection. FSH will offer partners IPR support over the course of the project (M18, M30) through workshops that will provide information on the basics of IPR, rules to consider and the process to seek protection. Detailed consultation services will not be provided, as IPR protection requires legal expertise.

6 Conclusion

D5.1 “Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities”, has provided an overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The intention of this document is to outline the initial DEC plan which will be implemented during the first period of the BioRural project, as well as the tools that will be utilized to reach DEC’s KPIs and project’s audience.

More specifically, the document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of BioRural aiming to assure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximize the impact.

The Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (D5.2), due in M18, will be an updated version of the DEC plan. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M18 until the third iteration (M36). The final update (D5.3) “Results of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities” will focus on the diffusion of the information and knowledge generated by the creation of the ERBN and the 4 RBNs as well as by the development of the BioRural Toolkit.

Annex A: Logo variations

Annex B: BioRural's covers

Annex C: Dissemination and Communication material

Brochure sides A&B

Expected results

- 1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network
- 4 Regional Bioeconomy Platforms
- 20 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories
- 42 Capacity building workshops
- 4 Regional workshops
- 1 European Bioeconomy Challenge
- 440 Interviews with end users/experts
- 5 Knowledge exchange workshops
- 5 Bioeconomy business models
- Policy recommendations
- >400 Bioeconomy material
- Filmed workshops
- 8 Success stories videos
- Integration with EU's knowledge centre for Bioeconomy

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Connecting the dots to

UNLOCK THE POTENTIAL

of European rural areas

towards circular

BIOECONOMY

Register to BioRural's Bioeconomy platform to join European BioEconomy networks!

[biorural.eu](https://www.biorural.eu)

[in biorural](#)
[@bio_rural](#)
[f bioruraleu](#)
[BioRural](#)
[BioRural channel](#)

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A Horizon Europe Project
1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025

Funded by the European Union

Introduction

"The bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy" (EC) and a thriving bioeconomy is key to creating a circular European economy

Challenges

- Our economies are based on linear production systems using non-renewable resources
- Rural areas face acute demographic, poverty and climate challenges
- Rural bioeconomy knowledge and technology transfer is not adequately supported

...but opportunities exist

- Circular Bioeconomy solutions and networks exist
- Increased policy, research and innovation support for a circular Bioeconomy
- New bio-based innovations are consistently supporting the transition to a circular economy

Objective

"BioRural's goal is to create a European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of the Bioeconomy"

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate the current status of the European Bioeconomy
- Identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions
- Create a European rural Bioeconomy network
- Assess and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building for the rural Bioeconomy
- Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool (BioRural Toolkit)
- Create rural development blueprints for Bioeconomy businesses from conception to scale

Approach

BioRural is centered on three pillars that feed into a publicly available BioRural Toolkit

Pillars

Pillar 1: Knowledge

- Information gap analysis
- Knowledge exchange workshops
- BioRural Toolkit

Pillar 2: Network

- 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
- Circular success stories
- Synergies with previous and ongoing innovative bio-economy projects
- Capacity building and regional workshops, Bioeconomy challenge

Pillar 3: Business Models

- Business model blueprints for each theme
- Post-project sustainability

Banner

BIOrural
Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Knowledge
Network
Business Models
BIOrural Toolkit

Connecting the dots to
UNLOCK THE POTENTIAL
of European rural areas
towards circular
BIOECONOMY

Funded by the European Union
<https://biorural.eu>

Press release template

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Social Media

Facebook	BioRural
Twitter	bio_rural
LinkedIn	BioRural
YouTube	BioRural

www.biorural.eu

Annex D: Deliverable template

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Enter your deliverable title here

Responsible Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner's short name)]

biorural.eu

BioRural DX.X: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101060166
Project Acronym	BioRural
Project Title	Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas
Type of action	CSA - Coordination and Support Actions
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBI0-01-06: Mainstreaming inclusive small-scale bio-based solutions in European rural areas
Start – ending date	1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025
Project Website	https://biorural.eu/
Work Package	WPx: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Relevant Task(s)	Tx: Title of the Task
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R - Report, DEC: Websites, press & media actions, videos, OTHER: Software, etc. PU: Public; SEN: Sensitive; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
Actual Submission Date	DD Month 20YY
Responsible Author	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]
Reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.1	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.X	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)

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BioRural Consortium DX.X: Deliverable Title

Participant Nr.	Participant organization name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALDRIAL	VALDRIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	IZES GMBH	IZES	DE
6	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG-PIB	PL
8	VYTAUTO DIDZIOKO UNIVERSITETAS	Vytauto	LT
9	LATVIJAS LAUKSAIMNIECIBAS UNIVERSITATE	LLU	LV
10	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA	AVEBIOM	ES
11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA	CBE	PT
13	AIEL - ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	FOODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KEROSOKOPIKI ETAREIA	FSH	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICO	EL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	LJL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA ALGNE TEHNOLOGIJE, DOO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO
19	ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJ SLOPIJE	GGP	MK

BioRural DX.X: Deliverable Title

Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

BioRural DX.X: Deliverable Title

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List of Figures

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List of Tables

Table 2: Example caption for tables 8

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1

BioRural DX.X: Deliverable Title

1 Heading 1

1.1 Heading 2

1.1.1 Heading 3

1.1.1.1 Heading 4

1.1.1.1.1 Heading 5

1.1.1.1.1.1 Heading 6

Title #1	Title #2

Table 1: Example caption for tables

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

Annex E: Event Planning Template

BioRural EVENT PLANNING

Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of, and feel would be well suited for BioRural participation.

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

Annex F: Synergy Mapping Template

BioRural SYNERGY MAPPING

Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Annex G: Publication Planning Template

BioRural PUBLICATION PLANNING

Please complete the following form with peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other publication you plan to make.

BioRural Publication Planning			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date

Annex H: BioRural brand book

colors

CMYK

	0 50 100 0
	0 40 60 0
	0 20 100 0
	0 60 60 40
	0 100 100 30
	80 25 100 10
	90 0 100 0
	60 0 95 0
	60 0 5 0
	30 0 10 0

#Hex

#DA9027	
#E1A86E	
#EFCA1E	
#955D4A	
#9A282C	
#66873F	
#54A148	
#92B849	
#8AC5E8	
#C7E2E7	

typeface

iCiel Gotham Thin
(outlined with round corners and round caps)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee
Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy
Zz

Example

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions
integration in European rural areas

Annex I: Identification of new KERs & IPR process

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation					Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation (how)	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
KER no	Please add any other exploitable results if relevant	Scientific	Commercial	Policy making	Training	other (please specify)	For additional KERs please see note for the list of target groups	For additional KERs please describe the means of exploitation.	Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant (one KER might be subject to more than one type of IPR)		
									IPR	IPR	if other please specify